

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Numerical solution of a mixed problem for a hyperbolic system with dynamic boundary conditions

Aloev R.Dj., Ovlaeva M.Kh.

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
 aloyevr@mail.ru, mohinur1009@gmail.com

Annotatsiya.

This article is devoted to hyperbolic systems controlled by dynamic boundary conditions. A finite-difference scheme is proposed for the numerical solution of such systems, and the exponential stability of the numerical solution is investigated. Using the Lyapunov function introduced in this work, the stability of the finite-difference scheme is analyzed. Based on the theory of Lyapunov stability, sufficient conditions for the exponential stability of the numerical solution of such systems are obtained. A computational program implementing the proposed finite-difference scheme is developed, and numerical experiments are conducted to validate the results.

Keywords: Lyapunov function, Riemann invariants, linear hyperbolic system, dynamic boundary condition, initial condition

1. Introduction

References [1]–[3] study the exponential stability of one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic systems, using Lyapunov functions and considering both standard and dynamic boundary conditions. Reference [2] extends stability analysis to systems with small non-homogeneous perturbations, applied to water flow control in open channels. References [4]–[5] address control problems, demonstrating the effectiveness of observers and controllers via PDE modeling. References [6]–[13] focus on numerical solutions, constructing difference schemes and discrete Lyapunov functions to ensure stability and convergence in Sobolev spaces. These studies primarily consider standard boundary conditions. This article extends prior results to discrete hyperbolic systems with dynamic boundary conditions, providing a unified framework for stability analysis.

2. Statement of the problem Consider the following linear hyperbolic system of equations in Riemannian coordinates:

$$\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial t} + \Lambda \frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \forall x \in [0, 1], t \geq 0. \quad (1)$$

where Λ is the diagonal and invertible matrix of dimension $n \times n$, such that

$$\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n) \\ \lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots < \lambda_{m-1} < \lambda_m < 0 < \lambda_{m+1} < \lambda_{m+2} < \dots < \lambda_n. \quad (2)$$

Let $m = 0$.

The unknown vector function V is represented in the following form $V(x, t) = \begin{bmatrix} V^I(x, t) \\ V^{II}(x, t) \end{bmatrix}$, $V^I = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m)^T$, $V^{II} = (v_{m+1}, v_{m+2}, \dots, v_n)^T$.

Let us introduce the following notation

$$|\Lambda| = \text{diag}(|\lambda_1|, |\lambda_2|, \dots, |\lambda_n|). \quad (3)$$

The problem of stability of linear hyperbolic systems was considered, in particular, in [1,2,3] using static boundary conditions defined as

$$\begin{bmatrix} V^I(1, t) \\ V^{II}(0, t) \end{bmatrix} = S \begin{bmatrix} V^I(0, t) \\ V^{II}(1, t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

for a given matrix S of dimension $n \times n$.

Linear hyperbolic systems with dynamics related to the boundary conditions are less studied in the literature, although there are approaches using finite-dimensional approximations, e.g. in [4], that have successfully stabilized such systems:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} V^I(1, t) \\ V^{II}(0, t) \end{bmatrix} = A \begin{bmatrix} V^I(1, t) \\ V^{II}(0, t) \end{bmatrix} + B \begin{bmatrix} V^I(0, t) \\ V^{II}(1, t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

Let a continuously differentiable function V^0 be given that satisfies the conditions of matching (both the function itself and its first derivative) of the initial and boundary conditions; the initial conditions can be defined as

$$V(x, 0) = V^0(x), \quad \forall x \in [0, 1], \quad V^0(x) = (v_1^0(x), v_2^0(x), \dots, v_n^0(x))^T. \quad (6)$$

The study in (5) is devoted to the analysis of stability of (1), (5), and (6) using the Lyapunov functions. It formulates a sufficient condition for exponential stability of (1), (5), and (6).

Difference scheme

Consider the mixed problem (1), (5), and (6).

In the domain $G = \{(t, x) : 0 \leq t \leq T, 0 \leq x \leq L\}$, we construct a difference grid with steps Δt in the direction t and Δx in the direction x . The nodal points of the difference grid (the intersection of straight lines $t = t^\kappa = \kappa \Delta t$ and $x = x_j = j \Delta x$) are denoted by (x_j, t^κ) . The set of nodal points of the difference grid is denoted by G_h , where

$$G_h = \{(x_j, t^\kappa) : \kappa = 0, \dots, N; j = 0, \dots, J\},$$

and the values of the numerical solution at the nodal points are denoted by

$$V_j^\kappa = V(x_j, t^\kappa), \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N, \quad j = 0, \dots, J.$$

The steps of the difference grid Δt and Δx are selected in such a way that the equalities $N \Delta t = T$, $J \Delta x = L$ are fulfilled.

To find a numerical solution to the mixed problem (1), (5) and (6) over the difference grid G_h , we propose the following difference scheme:

$$(v_i)_{j}^{\kappa+1} = (v_i)_{j}^{\kappa} - \lambda_i \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \left[(v_i)_{j}^{\kappa+1} - (v_i)_{j-1}^{\kappa+1} \right], \quad j = \overline{1, J}, \quad \kappa = \overline{0, N-1}, \quad i = \overline{1, n}. \quad (7)$$

or in a vector form

$$V_j^{\kappa+1} = V_j^{\kappa} - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \Lambda \left[V_j^{\kappa+1} - V_{j-1}^{\kappa+1} \right], \quad j = \overline{1, J}, \quad \kappa = \overline{0, N-1}. \quad (8)$$

Initial conditions (5) are approximated as follows:

$$(v_i)_j^0 = v_i^0(x_j), \quad j = \overline{0, J}, \quad i = \overline{1, n}, \quad (9)$$

or in a vector form

$$V_j^0 = V^0(x_j), \quad j = \overline{0, J}. \quad (10)$$

The boundary conditions are approximated in the following way:

$$\frac{V_0^{\kappa+1} - V_0^{\kappa}}{\Delta t} = AV_0^{\kappa+1} + BV_J^{\kappa+1}, \quad \kappa = \overline{1, N-1}. \quad (11)$$

The theorem on the exponential stability of this difference scheme and its proof are presented in [12].

Model problem and algorithm for its numerical solution

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + 4 \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

We consider the system. As the initial condition, we take

$$v(x, 0) = e^x, \quad u(x, 0) = e^{3x}. \quad (16)$$

The dynamic boundary conditions at $x = 0$ are given as follows

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial v(0, t)}{\partial t} = -3v(0, t) - 2u(0, t) - e^{-1}v(1, t) + 2e^{-3}u(1, t), \\ \frac{\partial u(0, t)}{\partial t} = -v(0, t) - \frac{1}{2}u(0, t) + e^{-1}v(1, t) - \frac{1}{2}e^{-3}u(1, t). \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

To numerically solve the mixed problem given by (15), (16), and (17), we use the finite-difference schemes (8), (10), and (11). Using these schemes, the numerical solution of the mixed problem (15)–(17) is obtained at the $\{V_j^{\kappa}, j = \overline{0, J}, \kappa = \overline{0, N}\}$ grid points, corresponding to $\{(x_j, t^{\kappa}) : j = \overline{0, J}, \kappa = \overline{0, N}\}$ nodes of the finite-difference mesh. The schemes (8), (10), and (11) are applied to the mixed problem (15)–(17) as follows:

The finite-difference system (8) is written as

$$\begin{cases} v_j^{\kappa+1} = v_j^{\kappa} - 4 \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} [v_j^{\kappa+1} - v_{j-1}^{\kappa+1}], & j = \overline{1, J}, \quad \kappa = \overline{0, N-1}, \\ u_j^{\kappa+1} = u_j^{\kappa} - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} [u_j^{\kappa+1} - u_{j-1}^{\kappa+1}], & j = \overline{1, J}, \quad \kappa = \overline{0, N-1}. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

with the initial conditions (10) given by

$$\begin{cases} v_j^0 = e^{x_j}, \\ u_j^0 = e^{3x_j}, \end{cases} \quad j = \overline{0, J}, \quad (19)$$

and the boundary conditions (11) written as

$$\begin{cases} \frac{v_0^{\kappa+1} - v_0^\kappa}{\Delta t} = -3v_0^{\kappa+1} - 2u_0^{\kappa+1} - e^{-1}v_J^{\kappa+1} + 2e^{-3}u_J^{\kappa+1}, \\ \frac{u_0^{\kappa+1} - u_0^\kappa}{\Delta t} = -v_0^{\kappa+1} - \frac{1}{2}u_0^{\kappa+1} + e^{-1}v_J^{\kappa+1} - \frac{1}{2}e^{-3}u_J^{\kappa+1}, \end{cases} \quad k = \overline{0, N-1}. \quad (20)$$

We develop a program that computes all the grid points based on (18)–(20) and run it. The numerical solution obtained in this way yields the following results.

Figure 1. Surface plots of the numerical solutions $u(x,t)$ and $v(x,t)$

This figure shows the numerical solutions of the functions $u(x,t)$ (left) and $v(x,t)$ (right), computed using the proposed finite-difference scheme. The surfaces illustrate the evolution of the solutions in space and time, clearly demonstrating their decay under dynamic boundary conditions. Fig. 2 presents the time evolution of the norm of the numerical solution. The rapid decrease of the norm indicates the exponential stability of the computed solution, confirming the theoretical results obtained via the Lyapunov approach

Figure 2. Norm of the numerical solution

Conclusion. In this paper, a linear hyperbolic system with dynamic boundary conditions was studied. A finite-difference scheme was developed for the numerical solution of the system, and the exponential stability of the numerical solution was investigated. The stability of the finite-difference scheme was analyzed using a discrete Lyapunov function. A numerical example was implemented using the proposed scheme, and numerical results were obtained. For this purpose, the D-GipTS (Dynamic Hyperbolic PDE System) program was developed to compute the numerical solutions.

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